

De La Warre's description of treating scurvy with oranges and lemons (1611)

by Harri Hemilä

Thomas West, 3rd Baron De La Warr was an English colonial administrator after whom the Delaware Bay, the Delaware River, a Native American people known as the Delaware, and the U.S. state of Delaware were named. He served as the governor of the Colony of Virginia from 1610 to 1611. Suffering from scurvy, he returned to London in 1611 and composed a report defending his decision to leave the colony. A copy of that report is reproduced in this document.

Lord De La Warre's description of treatment of scurvy with orange and lemon was cited in:

When, in 1611, the new Lord Governor of Virginia arrived in Jamestown he had developed scurvy and promptly shipped himself to the West Indies where 'I found help for my health and my sickness assuaged, by means of fresh diet, and especially of oranges and lemons, an undoubted remedy and medicine for that disease, which lastly, and for so long, had affected me.'

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment. *Nutr Rev.* 2009;67:315-32.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

"Lord De La Warre, who had been put in charge of the plantation (colony) of Virginia, returned home unexpectedly in 1611. His explanation to his sponsors was that he had been forced to do so by ill health. On his first arrival in Jamestown, he was 'welcomed' by a violent ague (malaria?), which would come and go; then he had dysentery, followed by cramps and gout: 'These making my body through weakness unable to stir ... drew upon me the disease called the scurvy.' His friends told him that 'wanting [lacking] both food and physic fit to remedy such extraordinary diseases,' he should go to the West Indies to recover. 'There I found help for my health, by means of fresh diet, and especially of oranges and lemons ... an undoubted remedy for that disease,' but his friends still advised him that, before returning to Virginia, he should seek to recover his strength completely 'in the natural air of my country.' One can imagine that worse things happened to less privileged men, but their story has gone unrecorded."

Carpenter KJ (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C.* 1986, p.12.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

Biographies

“Thomas West, 3rd Baron De La Warr (1576–1618) was an English colonial administrator for whom the bay,¹ the river,² and, consequently, a Native American people³ and U.S. state,⁴ all later called ‘Delaware’, were named. A member of the House of Lords, from the death of his father in 1602 until his own death in 1618, he served as the governor of Virginia from 1610 to 1611...

He left the colony on a ship captained by Argall headed to the West Indies to recover but was blown off course by a storm, ending up in Faial Island, Azores. De La Warr returned to London, England in June, 1611. He requested a private audience from King James I to explain why he wasn't governing in Virginia. He was summoned by the Virginia Company where he explained his health conditions (‘flux’, cramps, gout, and scurvy) in detail and his diet of oranges and lemons in the Azores helped him recover.”

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_West,_3rd_Baron_De_La_Warr

“Chronic ill health, including dysentery and scurvy, drove De La Warr to flee the colony in the spring of 1611 in search of relief. His abrupt return to London caused such consternation in the company that later in the year he defended himself by publishing *The Relation of the Right Honourable the Lord De La-Warre, Lord Governour and Captaine Generall of the Colonie, Planted in Virginea.*”

<https://encyclopediavirginia.org/entries/west-thomas-twelfth-baron-de-la-warr-1576-1618/>

Lord Delaware, First Governor of Virginia, “the Poorest Baron of this Kingdom.”
The Virginia Magazine of History and Biography, 128(3), 226–258.

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26926494>

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Thomas-West-12th-Baron-De-La-Warr>

The relation of the Right Honourable the Lord De-La-Warre, lord gouvernour and captaine generall of the colonie, planted in Virginea

De La Warre’s text is available at:

Original version:

https://archive.org/details/relationofrighth00dela_0/page/n7/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/relationofrighth00dela/page/n7/mode/2up>

<https://name.umdl.umich.edu/A14958.0001.001>

Somewhat modernized version:

<https://encyclopediavirginia.org/primary-documents/relation-of-the-right-honourable-the-lord-d-la-warre-lord-governour-and-captaine-generall-of-the-colonie-planted-in-virginea-the-1611/>

https://americanjourneys.org/AJ_PDF/aj-076.pdf

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delaware_Bay

2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delaware_River

3 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lenape>

4 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delaware>

A
SHORT RE-
lation made by the
Lord *De-La-Warre*, to the Lords
and others of the Counsell of *Virginea*,
touching his vnexpected returne home, and af-
terwards deliuered to the generall Assembly
of the said Company, at a Court holden
the twenty five of Iune,
1611.

Published by authority of
the said Counsell.

My Lords, &c.

Being now by accident returned
from my Charge at *Virginea*, con-
trary either to my owne desire, or

other mens expectations, who spare not
to censure me, in point of duty, and to dis-
course and question the reason, though
they apprehend not the true cause of my
returne, I am forced, (out of a willingnesse
to satisfie euery man) to deliuer vnto your
Lordships, and the rest of this Assembly,
briefely, (but truely) in what state I haue
liued, euer since my arriuall to the *Colonie*;
what hath beene the iust occasion of my
sudden departure thence; and in what
termes I haue left the same: The ra-
ther because I perceiue, that since my com-
ming into *England*, such a coldnesse and
irresolution is bred, in many of the *Aduentu-*
rers, that some of them seeke to withdraw
those paimēts,⁵ which they haue subscribed

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5 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/paiement>

towards the Charge of the *Plantation*, and by which that *Action* must bee supported and maintained; making this my returne,

the colour of their needlesse backwardnes and vniust⁶ protraction. Which, that you may the better vnderstand, I must informe your Lordships, that presently after my arriual in *James Towne*,⁷ I was welcommed by a hote and violent Ague, which held mee a time, till by the aduice of my Physition, Doctor *Laurence Bohun*, (by blood letting) I was recouered, as in my first Letters by Sir *Thomas Gates*⁸ I haue informed you. That disease had not long left me, til (with- in three weekes after I had gotten a little strength) I began to be distempered with other greeuous sicknesses, which succes- siuely & seuerally assailed me: for besides a relapse into the former disease, which with much more violence held me more then a moneth, and brought me to great weakenesse, the Flux⁹ surprised me, and kept

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me many daies; then the Crampe assaulted my weak body, with strong paines; & after- wards the Gout (with which I had heere- tofore beene sometime troubled) afflicted mee in such sort, that making my body through weakenesse vnable to stirre, or to vse any maner of exercise, drew vpon me the disease called the Scuruy; which though in others it be a sicknesse of slothfulnesse,¹⁰ yet was in me an effect of weaknesse, which neuer left me, till I was vpon the point to leaue the world.

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6 Vniust. Unjust.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/vniust>

7 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jamestown,_Virginia

<https://www.britannica.com/place/Jamestown-Colony>

8 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Gates_\(governor\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Gates_(governor))

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Thomas-Gates>

<https://encyclopediaivirginia.org/entries/gates-sir-thomas-d-1622/>

9 Flux. Diarrhea.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/flux>

10 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/slothful>

These seuerall maladies and calamities,
I am the more desirous to particularise vnto
your Lordships (although they were too
notorious to the whole *Colonie*) left any
man should misdeeme that vnder the ge-
neral name and cōmon excuse of sicknes,
I went about to cloke¹¹ either sloth, or feare,

or anie other base apprehension, vn-
worthy the high and Generall charge,
which you had entrusted to my Fide-
litie.

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In these extremities I resolved to con-
sult my friends, who (finding Nature
spent in mee, and my body almost con-
sumed, my paines likewise daily encrea-
sing) gaue me aduise to preferre a hope-
full recouery, before an assured ruine,
which must necessarily had ensued, had
I liued, but twenty dayes longer, in *Vir-
ginia*: wanting at that instant, both food
and *Physicke*, fit to remedy such extraor-
dinary diseases, and restore that strength
so desperately decayed.

Whereupon, after a long consulta-
tion held, I resolved by generall consent
and perswasion, to shippe my selfe for

Meuis,¹² an Island in the West Indies,
famous for wholesome Bathes, there to
try what help the Heauenly Prouidence
would afford mee, by the benefit of the
hot Bath: But GOD, who guideth all
things, according to his good will and
pleasure, so prouided, that after wee had
sailed an hundred Leagues,¹³ wee met with
Southerly windes which forced mee to
change my purpose, (my body being al-
together vnable to endure the tedious-
nesse of a long voyage) and so sterne my
course for the Western Islands, which

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11 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/cloke>

12 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nevis>

13 1 League is about 5 km.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/English_units_of_measurement#Length

I no sooner recouered, then I found help for my health, and my sicknesse asswaged, by meanes of fresh diet, and especially of Oreniges and Lemonds, an vndoubted remedy and medicine for that disease, which lastly, and so long, had

afflicted mee: which ease as soone as I found, I resolued (although my body remained still feeble and weake), to returne backe to my charge in *Virginia* againe, but I was aduised not to hazard my selfe before I had perfectly recouered my strength, which by counsell I was perswaded to seeke in the naturall Ayre of my Countrey, and so I came for England. In which Accident, I doubt not but men of reason, and of iudgement will imagine, there would more danger and preiudice haue hapned by my death there, then I hope can doe by my returne.

In the next place, I am to giue accompt in what estate I left the *Collony* for gouernment in my absence. It may please your Lordships therefore to vnderstand,

that vpon my departure thence, I made choise of Captaine *George Peartie*, (a Gentleman of honour and resolution, and of no small experience in that place) to remaine Deputie Gouvernour, vntill the comming of the Marshall Sir *Thomas Dale*,¹⁴ whose Commission was likewise to be determined, vpon the arriual of Sir *Thomas Gates*, according to the intent and order of your Lordships, and the Council here.

The number of men I left there, were vpward of two hundred, the most in health, and prouided of at least tenne moneths victuals, in their store-house,

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14 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Dale
<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Thomas-Dale>
<https://encyclopediavirginia.org/entries/dale-sir-thomas-d-1619/>

(which is daily issued vnto them)
besides other helps in the Countrey, lately found out by Captaine *Argoll* by trading with pettie Kings in those parts,

who for a small returne of a piece of Iron, Copper, &c. haue consented to trucke great quantities of Corne, and willingly imbrace the intercourse of Traffique, shewing vnto our people certaine signes of amitie and affection.

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And for the better strengthening and securing of the *Collony*, in the time of my weaknesse there, I tooke order for the building of three seuerall Forts, two of which are seated neere *Poynt Comfort*,¹⁵ to which adioyneth a large Circuit of ground, open, and fit for Corne: the third Fort is at the *Falles*, vpon an Iland inuironed also with Corne ground. These are not all manned, for I wanted the commoditie of Boates, hauing but two, and one Bardge, in all the Countrey, which hath bene cause that our

fishing hath bene (in some sort) hindered, for want of those prouisions, which easily will be remedied when wee can gaine sufficient men to be employed about those businesses, which in *Virginia* I found not: but since meeting with Sir *Thomas Gates* at the Cowes neere *Portsmouth* (to whom I gaue a perticular accompt of all my proceedings, and of the present estate of the *Collony* as I left it) I vnderstood those wants are supplied in his Fleete.

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The Countrey is wonderfull fertile and very rich, and makes good whatsoever heretofore hath bene reported of it, the Cattell already there, are much encreased, and thriue exceedingly with the pasture of that Countrey: The Kine¹⁶ all

15 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Old_Point_Comfort

16 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/kine>

this last Winter, though the ground

was couered most with Snow, and the season sharpe, liued without other feeding then the grasse they found, with which they prospered well, and many of them readie to fall with Calue: Milke being a great nourishment and refreshing to our people, seruing also (in occasion) as well for *Physicke* as for food, so that it is no way to be doubted, but when it shall please God that Sir *Thomas Dale*, and Sir *Thomas Gates*, shall arriue in *Virginia* with their extraordinary supply of one hundred Kine, and two hundred Swine, besides store of all manner of other prouisions for the sustenance and maintenance of the *Collony*, there will appeare that successe in the Action as shall giue no man cause of distrust that hath already aduentured, but encourage

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euery good minde to further so worthy a worke, as will redound both to the Glory of GOD, to the Credit of our Nation, and to the Comfort of all those that haue beene Instruments in the furthering of it.

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The last discouery, during my continuall sicknesse, was by Captaine *Argoll*, who hath found a trade with *Patamack*¹⁷ (a King as great as *Powhatan*,¹⁸ who still remaines our enemie, though not able to doe vs hurt.) This is in a goodly Riuer called *Patomack*,¹⁹ vpon the borders whereof there are growne the goodliest Trees for Masts, that may be found elsewhere in the World: Hempe better then English, growing wilde in abundance: Mines of Antimonie and Leade without our Bay to the Northward.

17 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Patawomeck>

18 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Powhatan>

19 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Potomac_River

There is also found an excellent fishing Banke for Codde,²⁰ and Ling²¹ as good as can be eaten, and of a kinde that will keepe a whole yeare, in Shippes hould,²² with little care; a tryall whereof I now haue brought ouer with mee. Other Islands there are vpon our Coasts, that doe promise rich merchandise, and will further exceedingly the establishing of the *Plantation*, by supply of many helpes, and will speedily afford a returne of many worthie Commodities.

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I haue left much ground in part manured to receiue Corne, hauing caused it the last Winter to be sowed for rootes, with which our people were greatly releued.

There are many Vines planted in

diuers places, and doe prosper well, there is no want of any thing, if the action can be vpheld with constancy and resolution.

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Lastly, concerning my selfe, and my course, though the World may imagine that this Countrey and Climate, will (by that which I haue suffered beyond any other of that *Plantation*) ill agree, with the state of my body, yet I am so farre from shrinking or giuing ouer this honourable enterprise, as that I am willing and ready to lay all I am worth vpon the aduenture of the Action, rather then so Honourable a worke should faile, and to returne with all the conuenient expedition I may, beseeching your Lordships, and the rest, not onely to excuse my former wants, happened

by the Almighty hand: but to second my resolutions with your friendly

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20 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/codde>

21 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Common_ling

22 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/hould>

indeauours: that both the State may
receiue Honour, your selues Profit, and
future Comfort, by being imployed
(though but as a weake Instrument) in
so great an Action.

And thus hauing plainely, truely,
and briefly, deliuered the cause of my
returne, with the state of our affayres,
as wee now stand, I hope euery wor-
thy and indifferent hearer, will by com-
paring my present resolution of returne,
with the necessitie of my comming home,
rest satisfied with this true and short
Declaration.

FINIS.